

Kinetics of Oxidation of Phenacyl Halides by Vanadium(v) in Sulphuric and Perchloric Acid Media

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A kinetic study of oxidation of phenacyl halides, namely, phenacyl chloride, phenacyl bromide and phenacyl iodide by vanadium(v) in acid medium, obeys first order with respect to [oxidant] and [substrate]. The reactions are acid-catalysed and various hypothesis for the mechanism of acid catalysis have been tested. The different reactivity of phenacyl halides is explained on the basis of different inductive effect felt by the carbon atom in phenacyl halide.

KINETICS of oxidation of many organic compounds by vanadium(v) have been reported¹. There is apparently no mention in the literature of kinetic studies on oxidation of phenacyl chloride and phenacyl iodide by any oxidant. However, the kinetic studies on oxidation of several phenacyl bromides have been studied by vanadium(v)^{2,3} and cerium(iv)⁴ in acid medium. This paper reports the oxidation of phenacyl chloride and phenacyl iodide and study on the effect on rate when bromine is replaced by chlorine or iodine from phenacyl bromide so that the reactivity of phenacyl halides can be compared.

Experimental

Phenacyl chloride and phenacyl bromide (Fluka) and ammonium metavanadate (Riedel) were used. Phenacyl iodide was prepared by the action of sodium iodide on phenacyl bromide in acetone medium⁵. The acetic acid (AnalaR) was refluxed twice and distilled with chromium trioxide. Other inorganic chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

A standard solution of vanadium(v) was prepared by dissolving ammonium metavanadate in standard sulphuric or perchloric acids. Solutions of phenacyl halides were prepared by dissolving the required amount of substrate in 100% acetic acid. Solutions of vanadium(v) and the reaction mixture containing phenacyl halide, acetic acid and sulphuric or perchloric acid were thermostated separately. The solutions were then mixed and at suitable intervals a portion of reaction mixture was withdrawn and quenched in phosphoric and sulphuric acid mixture containing a known excess of iron(II) ammonium sulphate. The unreacted iron(II) was then titrated against standard vanadium(v) solution using barium salt of diphenylamine sulphate as an indicator.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometric analysis of oxidation reaction between phenacyl halide and vanadium(v) in sulphuric or

perchloric acid medium revealed that three moles of vanadium(v) are required to oxidise one mole of phenacyl halide. The products of the reaction were found to be benzoic acid and formaldehyde. The identification of products was done by the usual methods^{6,7}. The stoichiometric equation may be written as

where, X represents a chlorine or bromine or iodine atom.

Results and Discussion

Phenacyl chloride, phenacyl bromide and phenacyl iodide do not undergo acid hydrolysis under the reaction conditions, i.e. in 1.0–5.0 M sulphuric or perchloric acid in presence of acetic acid medium. The oxidation reaction of phenacyl halides by vanadium(v) in 3 M sulphuric or 3 M perchloric acid containing 60% (v/v) acetic acid showed first order dependence in [vanadium(v)] as well as in each [phenacyl halide].

The rate of oxidation of phenacyl halides increases with the increase in the percentage of acetic acid (40–70%, v/v), i.e. the rate increases with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium and the plot of $\log k_1$ against $1/D$ is linear with positive slope indicating the reaction to be a cation-dipole⁸. The rate of oxidation also increases marginally with the addition of $NaHSO_4$ and $NaClO_4$. The plots of $\log k_1$ against ionic strength (μ) give fairly straight lines with positive slopes confirming the reaction to be of cation-dipole type⁷.

The rate of oxidation reaction of phenacyl halides by vanadium(v) increased with the increase in concentration of sulphuric or perchloric acid respectively (Table 1). The Hammett plots of $\log k_1$ against $-H_0$ were linear with slope values ranging from 1.0 to 1.24 for all the reactions in

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [ACID] ON k_1 IN VANADIUM(V) - PHENACYL HALIDE REACTIONS
[Vanadium(v)] = 0.004 M, [Phenacyl halide] = 0.015 M, CH₃COOH = 50% (v/v), Temp. = 318 K

Substrate	$k_1 (\times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1})$ at [acid]/M						Slopes of plots of		
	2.50	3.00	3.50	4.00	4.50	5.00	$\log k_1$ vs $-H_0$	$(\log k_1 + H_0)$ vs $-\log a_{H_2O}$	$(\log k_1 + H_0)$ vs $\log C_{H^+} + H_0$
Sulphuric acid medium									
Phenacyl chloride	6.90	12.50	22.60	41.80	71.20	118.00	1.06	-0.50	-0.09
Phenacyl bromide	1.26	2.59	4.83	8.64	16.60	25.50	1.15	-1.20	-0.21
Phenacyl iodide	1.10	2.15	4.30	8.06	15.00	23.80	1.10	-1.15	-0.16
Perchloric acid medium									
Phenacyl chloride	6.40	9.00	15.60	28.00	48.20	—	1.00	-0.20	-0.03
Phenacyl bromide	0.90	1.73	3.53	6.92	15.35	—	1.24	-2.30	-0.33
Phenacyl iodide	0.83	1.54	3.07	5.76	13.78	—	1.14	-1.55	-0.25

both the acid media. These unit slope values indicate that the absence of participation of water molecule in the rate-determining step⁹. This is also confirmed by the Bunnett and Bunnett-Olsen relations, i.e. the plots of $\log k_1 + H_0$ against $-\log a_{H_2O}$ and $\log k_1 + H_0$ against $H_0 + \log C_{H^+}$ are fairly linear with slope values ranging from -0.2 to -2.3 and -0.03 to 0.34, respectively. These slope values also indicate the absence of water molecule in the reaction steps.

The rate of oxidation is faster in sulphuric acid than in perchloric acid indicating the presence of different reactive species in different acid media. The reactive species of vanadium(v) proposed in sulphuric acid and perchloric acid are V(OH)₅HSO₄⁺ and V(OH)₅³⁺, respectively. The bisulphate complex of vanadium(v) in sulphuric acid medium, V(OH)₅HSO₄⁺ is thought to be a better oxidant than V(OH)₅³⁺.

Based on the above observations, a mechanism for oxidation of phenacyl halides which does not involve participation of water molecule in the slow step is proposed. According to Waters and Littler¹, there is a possibility for the formation of cyclic five-membered chelate ring transition state when there is linear dependence of rate on Hammett acidity function $-H_0$. This generalisation has been used here as a criterion for proposing the five-membered ring involving substrate and vanadium(v) in the transition state, which on C-C fission in slow step forms C₆H₅CO· radical and a less stable intermediate CH₂OHX (where, X is Cl or Br or I), which undergoes oxidation in subsequent fast steps and gives products as benzoic acid and formaldehyde respectively². The presence of free radicals was detected by the polymerisation of acrylonitrile when added to the reaction mixture. The general rate expression derived from the given mechanism is

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[V^V]}{dt} = k_s [C_6H_5COCH_2X][V^V]h_0$$

The order of reactivity observed in the phenacyl halides oxidation reactions is phenacyl chloride >> phenacyl bromide > phenacyl iodide under similar conditions (Table 1). The different reactivity of phenacyl halides may be explained on the basis of

different inductive effect felt by the carbon atom due to the presence of halide atom in the phenacyl halide.

The thermodynamic parameters, like ΔE_a^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger are calculated by determining rate constants at five different temperatures ranging from 308 to 328 K in both sulphuric acid and perchloric acid media separately. The activation energy values for the oxidation reaction of phenacyl chloride, phenacyl bromide and phenacyl iodide are 65.72, 67.06, 72.42 in sulphuric acid and 61.75, 66.98, 78.54 kJ mol⁻¹ in perchloric acid medium, whereas the ΔG^\ddagger values are 88.00, 90.00, 90.88 in sulphuric acid and 89.88, 90.67 and 91.80 kJ mol⁻¹ in perchloric acid medium, respectively. The ΔG^\ddagger values for all the phenacyl halides are in close agreement with one another, indicating that the same type of mechanism is operative in all the cases¹⁰. Since ΔE^\ddagger is a measure of the reactivity of the compound, a more reactive compound is expected to have lower ΔE^\ddagger value and a less reactive one the higher ΔE^\ddagger value. The rate obtained is in accordance with the expected trend. The ΔS^\ddagger values are all negative showing the loss of entropy during the foamation of the activated complex which is more polar than the reactants and hence strongly solvated resulting in an ordered structure.

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